

Role of Non-electrolytes in the Stability of Sols of As_2S_3 and Sb_2S_3

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Role of some non-electrolytes in the stability of sols of As_2S_3 and Sb_2S_3 has been examined quantitatively. The non-electrolytes used include acetamide, formamide and dioxan. The efficacy of these in the flocculation of the two sols has been examined by measurement of electrophoretic mobilities and extinction coefficients.

It has generally been observed that the flocculating concentration of electrolytes for a sol changes in the presence of some non-electrolytes presumably due to sensitization. The sensitization of sols by non-electrolytes was observed long back by Billitzer¹, Freundlich and Rona² and Weiser³ (cf. a recent study by Ghosh⁴). In literature it will be found that diversified views have been expressed by earlier workers regarding the effect of some non-electrolytes such as sugar on As_2S_3 sol while no such work has been done on Sb_2S_3 sol. So in the present investigation efforts have been made to study the effect of non-electrolytes such as acetamide, formamide and dioxan with a view to deduce more concrete results of flocculating concentration with arsenic and antimony trisulphide sols.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Materials* : Formamide and acetamide used were of Riedel (Germany) grade and dioxan used was of B.D.H. analar grade. Other materials were same as described in previous communications^{5,6}.

(b) *Extinction measurements* : Extinction measurements were carried out in the manner described earlier^{5,6}. In each measurement of extinction change with time, 2.5 ml. of the prepared sol was put into the optical cell (of an EEL colorimeter) containing 2.5 ml. mixture of electrolyte, water and non-electrolyte. All measurements were carried out using Ilford bright spectrum red filter No. 608. Extinction was set at zero for water in the beginning of the experiment and checking was made every time before starting with fresh samples and during experiments, if necessary. All measurements were carried out at room temperature i.e., 25°.

(c) *Electrophoretic mobility* : Mobility measurements were carried out by macro-electrophoretic method using constant current supply and potentiometer vacuum tube voltmeter as described previously^{5,6}.

1. Billitzer, *Z. Physikal Chem.*, 1903, **45**, 312.
2. H. Freundlich and P. Rona, *Biochem-Z.*, 1917, **81**, 87.
3. H. B. Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, **28**, 1253.
4. K. Chakravarti and B. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 559.
5. Daluja and Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 262.
6. Daluja and Srivastava, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1968, **41**, 17.

RESULTS

(a) *The stability factor W from turbidity measurements.*

The change of turbidity h , with time t , for a coagulation process, as already mentioned is given as follows⁷⁻¹⁰

$$h = 2.303 E = BN_1 V t^2 \left(1 + \frac{K_2 N_1 t}{W} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

To see the validity of this equation for coagulation of both the sols with typical inorganic electrolytes, the curves plotted between E and t and typical ones are given in figures 1, 2. The curves are found to be quite linear in the early stages thereby confirming the validity of above mentioned equation. Therefore, values obtained for dt/dE seem to be correct.

Fig. 1. Effect of $6 \times 10^{-5} M$ $AlCl_3$ on As_2S_3 sol in the presence of various concs. of dioxan
 Δ —0%, \blacksquare —1%, \times —5%, \circ —10%, \blacktriangle —20%, \square —40% by volume

Fig. 2. Effect of $6 \times 10^{-2} M$ $NaCl$ on Sb_2S_3 in presence of formamide
 \circ —0%, \bullet —10%, \blacktriangle —20%, \square —30% by volume

For both the sols $\log(dt/dE)$ has been plotted against logarithm of the concentration of barium chloride with and without the different concentrations of non-electrolytes viz., acetamide, formamide and dioxan. Only the representative plots have been given in figures 3 and 4 as all the curves show a similar trend. The stability factor W could also be calculated from the values of dt/dE with the help of equation

$$\log W = \log \frac{K''}{2.303} C^2 + \log (dt/dE)_{t \rightarrow 0} \quad \dots (2)$$

7. S. A. Troelstra and H. R. Kruyt, *Kolloid Beih.*, 1943, **54**, 225.
8. G. Oster, *J. Colloid. Sci.*, 1947, **2**, 290.
9. R. H. Ottewill and M. C. Rastogi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 880.
10. R. H. Ottewill and A. Watansbe, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1960, **170**, 38.

where C is the sol concentration expressed in g./ml. and K'' the constant. It is clear from these curves, that the stability decreases steadily with the increasing concentration of barium chloride till the curves become parallel to the log concentration axis where rapid flocculation is supposed to occur as predicted by Reerink and Overbeek¹¹.

Fig. 3. Effect on $BaCl_2$ on As_2S_3 sol in the presence of dioxan

—■—1.03%, —×—5.15%, —△—10.3%, —●—20.6%, —○—41.2%

Fig. 4. Effect of $BaCl_2$ on Sb_2S_3 sol in the presence of acetamide

—■—1%, —×—5%, —▲—10%, —●—20%

Flocculating concentration of barium chloride for both the sols in the presence of different concentrations of non-electrolytes is determined by extrapolation of two linear portions of the plot between $\log \left(\frac{dE}{dt} \right)_{t \rightarrow 0}$ and \log concentration where $W = 1$. The values obtained in this way for barium chloride in the presence of non-electrolytes are plotted against the concentrations of the non-electrolytes in figures 5 and 6.

Fig. 5. Flocculating concentration of $BaCl_2$ for As_2S_3 sol in the presence of non-electrolyte

—●—Acetamide, —▲—Formamide, —■—Dioxan conc. of $BaCl_2$ vs. conc. of non-electrolyte

Fig. 6. Flocculating conc. of $BaCl_2$ for Sb_2S_3 sol in presence of non-electrolytes.

—●—Acetamide, —▲—Formamide, —■—Dioxan.

Flocculating concentration of barium chloride obtained for arsenic trisulphide sol in the absence of non-electrolyte is $1.51 \times 10^{-3} M$ while that of antimony trisulphide sol is $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$.

To analyse the data obtained from coagulation experiments, an alternative method is to plot the extinction measurements at definite time interval after mixing the contents, for each concentration of electrolyte against the logarithm of the molar concentration of electrolyte¹⁰. Representative curves for E versus log concentration are depicted in figures 7-8. In general, it may be concluded from the above results that the changes in the values of barium chloride required to flocculate the sols in the presence of non-electrolytes is of a similar trend as concluded from the log (dt/dE) versus log C curves. It is found also from these curves in general that the maximum value of E increases with the increasing concentration of the non-electrolytes.

Fig. 7. Effect of $BaCl_2$ on As_2S_3 sol in presence of dioxan

—○—0%, —■—1.03%, —×—5.16%, —▲—10.3%, —●—20.6%, —□—41.2%
Extinction E vs. log conc. of $BaCl_2 M$

Fig. 8. Effect of $BaCl_2$ on Sb_2S_3 sol in presence of Acetamide..

—■—1%, —×—5%, —▲—10%, —●—20%

(b) *Effect of non-electrolytes viz., acetamide, formamide and dioxan on mobility measurements of arsenic trisulphide and antimony trisulphide sols :*

The mobility of the arsenic trisulphide sol at pH 3.8 in the absence of non-electrolytes is $6.2 (\mu/sec)/(V/cm)$. Similarly the mobility of antimony trisulphide sol at pH 3.4 is $5.67 (\mu/sec)/(V/cm)$ at 25° .

Changes in the mobility due to increasing concentrations of non-electrolytes are depicted in figures 9 and 10 (Table I) respectively for arsenic trisulphide and antimony trisulphide sols. In general, the values of mobilities decrease with the increasing concentrations of non-electrolytes.

TABLE I

Electrophoretic mobility values of the As_2S_3 and Sb_2S_3 sols in the presence of non-electrolytes at 25°

Non-electrolytes	As_2S_3 sol		Sb_2S_3 sol	
	Concentration % by gms	Mobility (μ /sec)/(V/cm)	Concentration	Mobility (μ /sec)/(V/cm)
Acetamide	—	6.20	—	5.67
	1.00	6.00	1.66	5.36
	5.00	5.09	5.00	4.58
	10.00	3.85	10.00	4.25
	15.00	3.53	15.00	3.94
	20.00	2.93	20.00	3.71
Formamide	25.00	2.47	30.00	3.22
	1.13	5.44	1.13	5.47
	5.66	4.05	5.66	4.76
	11.33	3.43	11.33	4.46
	17.00	3.20	17.00	4.14
	22.66	2.96	22.66	3.86
Dioxan	28.32	2.65	33.99	3.41
	1.03	6.10	1.03	4.88
	5.15	6.62	5.15	4.40
	10.30	5.60	10.30	3.90
	15.45	4.20	15.45	3.65
	20.62	2.69	20.60	3.07
	25.75	2.92	25.75	2.91
—	—	30.90	—	
—	—	41.20	1.92	

 Fig. 9. Effect of non-electrolytes on As_2S_3 sol.

—●—acetamide, —▲—Formamide, —■—Dioxan
Mobility versus conc. of non-electrolyte, % by wt.

 Fig. 10. Flocculating concentration of $BaCl_2$ for As_2S_3 sol in the presence of non-electrolyte

—●—Acetamide, —▲—Formamide, —■—Dioxan
Conc. of $BaCl_2$ vs. conc. of non-electrolyte.

DISCUSSION

Increase of flocculating values of barium chloride for both the sols with increase of acetamide or formamide concentration signifies that the rate of coagulation decreases. This may be intimately connected with protection or stabilization because if the stability of the colloid increases, the rate of coagulation will decrease. The dioxan results show that the increase of the dioxan initially increased the stability of the sols and at later stages it gives sensitisation effect. However, at still higher concentrations it gives stabilisation effect against aluminium chloride whereas acetamide shows the increasing stability at all concentrations. Therefore, it may be concluded that with the same non-electrolyte divergent results are obtained when NaCl and BaCl₂ are added to the two sols.

From the decrease of the mobility with the increasing concentrations of non-electrolytes both of higher dielectric constant (formamide), as well as of lower dielectric constant (acetamide, dioxan) it is obvious that the potential of the double layer is apparently not determined by the change in dielectric constant alone. Nor the small changes in viscosity can account for these results. Therefore, it seems reasonable that the charge density of the system will also change owing to a change in the dielectric constant with the addition of non-electrolyte and may be responsible for the rate of decrease of the electrophoretic mobilities.

In the presence of equal quantities of non-electrolytes (say 10%) the flocculating concentrations of barium chloride are in the order dioxan > formamide > acetamide for arsenic trisulphide sol and are in the order formamide > acetamide > dioxan for antimony trisulphide sol. This difference is again attributable to the difference in the charge density in the two sols.

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